

Using DMR++ to Access HDF4/5 Archival Data in the Cloud

Cloud computing makes data access easier but...

Older archival HDF4/5 file formats are often stored as large arrays of compressed numerical data. These files are also designed for distinct computing systems, hindering access to decade-long time-series data when compared to data stored in modern cloud-optimized formats like Web Object Stores (WOS).

DMR++ can help access these older files

- DMR++ is a software that outperforms cloud-optimized versions of HDF5 and achieves performance comparable to technologies like Zarr.
- DMR++ preserves the original file structure, a substantial benefit considering the vast quantity of archival files held by organizations like NASA.

How does DMR++ work?

- DMR++ subsets archival HDF4/5 files by storing the location of 'chunks' of binary data (individually compressed) in an XML (Extensible Markup Language) document.
- DMR++ software does not use the HDF libraries to read the data, so data can be stored on WOSs.
- Data referenced by a single DMR++ XML file can be held by more than one file/object, enabling seamless access to separately stored data. This can be used to augment older data stored in HDF4/5 that are missing georeferencing information.

Figure 1. Data referenced by a single DMR++ file.

Working with NASA data: Using Sidecar Data Files to replace API libraries

The Challenge with NASA Data

Application Programmer Interface (API) libraries are often needed to compute variables. These libraries are incompatible with WOS environments where DMR++ runs.

Our DMR++ Solution: A Sidecar Data File

Storing computed values in the DMR++ document or a companion file (a sidecar data file) makes them accessible like other variables and eliminates the need for specialized APIs.

How to Create a Sidecar Data File

First, check if the original DMR++ XML file needs a sidecar file. If required, we rebuild the DMR++ XML file to ensure the sidecar file information is merged into the original DMR++ file. See Figure 2.

Figure 2. HDF data has 'missing' georeferencing data written to a second 'sidecar' data file. The DMR++ metadata file then references both the original data and the new 'missing' data.

OPeNDAP
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OPeNDAP is a nonprofit that developed the OPeNDAP client/server software. DAP = "Data Access Protocol" is OPeNDAP's data transmission protocol. Hyrax is the server half of OPeNDAP.

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